

Children's Digital Skills

Safe and Positive use
of Digital Technologies
in Ireland and Italy

Children's, Parents', and Teachers' Perspectives on
Digital Skills, Social Mediation, and Policy Implications

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Foreword

Alex Cooney

CyberSafeKids welcomes the publication of this work, which provides much needed insight into how children can engage with technology in a safer and more positive way, despite the pervasive risks that the online world can present to children. The findings are very much in line with our own view that technology use isn't inherently bad for children but that they must be adequately equipped for it, and supported by parents, carers and educators, especially when they are young. It is essential that children are taught how to be digitally literate so that they can make the most of the many opportunities that the online world presents, as well as manage (with the support of a trusted adult in some cases) harm and risks they may encounter.

CyberSafeKids is an Irish charity established in 2015. Our mission is to make the online world safer for children and children safer online. We do this through education, giving voice to children's online experience and by being a fierce advocate for children's online safety. We equip children, and those with a duty of care for them, with the skills needed to navigate the online world in a safe and responsible manner, while making the case for stronger regulation and investment in digital literacy by Government.

This work has substantially contributed to our activities: it has provided us with up-to-date data and analysis to inform the development of our services.

This grant funding opportunity has provided us with an invaluable opportunity to work closely together on this important piece of research. We firmly believe that partnerships between academia/research institutes and organisations like ours – that are meeting the need on the ground – can be extremely beneficial in finding effective ways to respond to the rapidly evolving online environment.

This report is part of a larger project that is still in progress and that will continue to provide us with an opportunity to enhance our knowledge on the risks and opportunities of children's use of technologies, thereby allowing us to respond to children, their families, and their teachers' needs in a more impactful way.

Key Findings

Entertainment activities such as watching videos and playing online games represent preadolescents' most frequent online activities.

Tablets, game consoles and computers are the most used devices by 10/11-year-old children. Less than 77% have access to smartphones.

A safe and positive use of digital technologies is associated with preadolescents' overall well-being regardless of the country considered.

Children's use of digital technologies is overall positive in both countries.

In both countries, participant preadolescents have overall good levels of psycho-social well-being.

Children show medium level of digital skills and knowledge, with Irish children reporting higher digital skills than Italian children.

There are no significant differences between males and females. However, results suggested it is worth further exploring digital technology use among non-binary preadolescents.

Parents use a combination of active, restrictive, and monitoring mediation strategies. Children perceive slightly less restrictions than what is perceived by parents.

Parents perceive a slightly higher alignment with teachers regarding how to educate children on digital technologies use and safety and protection when compared with teachers.

Teachers report medium levels of satisfaction with school digital policies and curriculum, with Irish teachers being more satisfied than Italian teachers.

Introduction

Marina Everri and Valerie O'Brien

The public discourse is saturated with conversations around digital technologies and fear and anxieties that technologies will override our lives and those of our children. Parents feel increasingly pressured and responsible for protecting their children while struggling with a lack of knowledge on a rapidly changing societal scenario characterised by AI, virtual reality, voice capture systems, and who knows what else ready to be put in the market.

Teachers seem to oscillate between the need to educate and the need to have more specific training on the use of technologies. Media providers, on their side, compete fiercely to develop the next '*bleeding edge*' technology, often underestimating the risks; while governments know the clock is ticking and rush to approve measures to provide their citizens (*including children*) with protection on the online world.¹ Worries and risks combine with innovation and opportunities, thereby creating confusion about the right direction to take when it comes to educating young generations to a safer and positive use of technologies.

There is no doubt (*like it or not*) that digital technologies play a fundamental part in children's everyday life. Today's children have been born in the era of tablets and smartphones, it is likely they were on Facebook even whilst in their mothers' wombs or their birth was streamed live via Skype or other video calls system. The *sharenting*² phenomenon started with their parents. Their house was already full of devices once they entered this world. Therefore, the use of digital devices and the Internet cannot be considered as an issue pertaining to young generations only: both kids and grown-ups use digital devices in their daily lives.

Reports have shown that the gap between the youngest and the oldest generations regarding digital technologies use and Internet access has been progressively declining over the last decade (*e.g. Faverio, 2022; Vogels, 2019*). In fact, digital technologies have become embedded in peoples' everyday life tasks, routines, and relationships, and they do not only enable communication exchanges but they also structure and

recursively change societal practices. In other words, it is no longer possible to think of going to work without having our smartphone in our pocket; everyone is part of a WhatsApp group being that of their extended family, their colleagues, their children's school, etc.; and reading a newspaper or turning on the heater in our house can be done through apps installed on a smartphone. Therefore, adults and children are all in the same boat!

However, it is important to acknowledge that children have started owning their personal digital devices and using digital technologies in a more active and participatory way at a younger age (*Smahel et al., 2020; CyberSafeKids, 2021*). Children receive their first smartphone as a present around the age of 10/11 years; at that age they transition from childhood to preadolescence which means not only experiencing physical and psychological changes, but also becoming more socially active in the physical and in the online world. This can bring opportunities for pre-adolescents' cognitive and social development, but also potential risks and harm. However, children do not live in isolation. Families and schools are key developmental contexts for their growth; therefore, when it comes to better understanding the relation between children and digital technologies, and in particular safety and protection, parents and teachers cannot be left out of the picture.

In this sense, this research report wished to provide a comprehensive and '*multi-perspective*' account of children's digital skills and safer and positive use of technologies also involving parents and teachers. Children in the age range 10-11 years, their parents/guardian and primary school teachers were recruited in two countries, the Republic of Ireland and Italy. The choice of these two countries is based on previous collaborations between the University College Dublin and research institutions and schools based in Italy.

¹ See the recent European Commission Acts: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-services-act-package>

² *Sharenting* is a term used to refer to the habitual use of social media to share news, images, etc. of one's children.

Data presented in this report were collected in Spring 2022, after the last significant phase of schools and offices closure due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic marked a turning point in the way people now approach and use digital technologies in their everyday lives. Therefore, our findings can provide an interesting overview of the ways in which children, their parents/guardian and teachers used technologies in the aftermath of a critical global event in which everybody was obliged to depend on technologies for attending to different tasks and meeting different needs. Thanks to the support of schools and youth associations, we were able to recruit more than 700 children, 200 parents and 100 teachers in the two countries.

We developed and administered online questionnaires with scales aimed at investigating: children's access to devices and online activities, their digital skills, their well-being, and their perception of strategies that parents and teaches use to regulate the use of digital technologies. Similar scales were included in the parents' and teachers' questionnaires together with additional variables on how family and school collaborate and coordinate for educating to children's safety and protection. Also, we included aspects related to school policy on digital media to better understand similarities and differences across the two countries

and assess teachers' point of views on the usefulness of those measures. Results are presented both aggregating data from Ireland and Italy and comparing the two countries to allow for a better view of the trends across the considered dimensions.

The conclusions discuss policy and recommendations for key stakeholders, namely children, parents/carers, teachers, governments, and media providers. Our hope is that this work can provide a contribution to ongoing conversations among the key stakeholders, and that our findings can orient researchers and policy makers to continue to work on the directions outlined in this report.

University College Dublin
Ireland's Global University

Definition of Terms

We list the definition of the key constructs and abbreviations we used for this work.

Digital Technologies (DT)	Any type of digital tools like computers, smartphones, tablets that support Internet connection.
Digital Skills	What children can do with digital technologies; they include functional and critical competencies in several domains, namely technical and operational, programming, information navigation and processing, communication and interaction and content creation and production.
Digital Knowledge	What children know about digital technologies regarding their design and how they work; it includes three domains, namely information navigation and processing, communication and interaction and content creation and production.
Online Activities	What children do online using any type of devices. They refer to learning, creating, entertainment and communication.
Safe and Positive use of Digital Technologies (SPUDT)	It refers to the use of digital technologies when children experience protection from risks, having benefits from the use, being in control of the time spent online and having a trusted adult to talk to in case of need.
Psychological Well-being	It refers to a positive state of mind when children experience positive emotions and a positive outlook.
Social Success	It refers to children's perception of being effective in their social contexts, namely having good social relationships and friends.
Active Mediation and Restrictive Mediation	They refer to two different types of adult mediation strategy to regulate children's use of digital technologies. The active mediation involves the active involvement of adults (i.e., parents and teachers) in talking to children about how to use digital technologies, whereas restrictive mediation involves limiting or banning the use of digital devices and online platforms.
Acceptable Use Policy (AUP)	Policy in place at school that regulate how to use digital technologies in school.
Digital Learning Plan (DLP)	Plan in place at school to teach children how to use digital technologies.

Please Note: In this report we use the terms preadolescents and children to refer to the same sample of participant children aged 10/11 years. Also, the term parents also includes children's guardians.

Theoretical Background

The theoretical background of this study is Activity Theory applied to the use of technology (Yardi & Bruckman, 2011). It is an ecological approach rooted in historical-cultural psychology (Vygotsky, 1978) which considers both personal and environmental factors to better understand people's behaviour. This model is based on seven different components that will be addressed in the report:

- 1 SUBJECT** The focus is on 10/11-year-old children.
- 2 OBJECT** The core aspect is DT use, namely what children do online (*i.e.*, *online activities*) and what children can do using DT (*namely digital skills*).
- 3 TOOLS** Online activities are carried out using different digital devices (*e.g.*, *smartphones, tablets, laptops...*) in different places (*i.e.* *at home, at school*) and availing of knowledge about how technology works.
- 4 COMMUNITY** Parents and teachers are involved in regulating children's access to digital devices use while at the same time being DT users.
- 5 DIVISION OF LABOUR** Members of the community (parents and teachers) coordinate with the aim of regulating children's online activities and teaching them how to best use DT.
- 6 RULES** Members of the community set strategies (*i.e.*, parental and teacher mediation strategies and school policies) to better regulate children's online activities.
- 7 OUTCOME** This refers to children's safe and positive use of DT.

A visual representation of the model is provided in Appendix.

Methodology

This report is based on findings from online surveys conducted with 10/11 year-old children, their parents and primary school teachers in the Republic of Ireland and Italy. Data was collected from March to June 2022.

Questionnaires

Questionnaires were designed in three versions to address the three different targets of the study. They were developed by two authors of this report in collaboration with CyberSafeKids' Education Team and they included both validated scales from the literature and questions devised ad hoc (*details on the structure are presented below*). From May 2021 to January 2022, questionnaires were tested on small samples through a pilot study.

Child Questionnaire

The questionnaire designed for children included 4 main sections:

- 1** The first was about online activities and safe and positive use of technology. As for **online activities**, core questions from the Global Kids Online Modular Survey (Byrne et al., 2016) were included, whereas items to measure **safe and positive use of digital technologies** were devised *ad hoc*.
- 2** The second section was about **digital skills and knowledge**. In this case, the Youth Digital Skills Indicator (*Helsper et al., 2020*) was adapted to be suitable for 10/11-year-olds. It included items related to five types of digital skills (*i.e.*, technical and operational, programming, information navigation and processing, communication and interaction, and content creation and production) and three types of digital knowledge (*i.e.*, information navigation and processing, communication and interaction, and content creation and production).

- 3 The third section was about **parental and teachers' mediation** strategies, and included items on parental enabling/active mediation, parental restrictive mediation and teacher enabling/active mediation and rules, all retrieved from the Global Kids Online Modular Survey (Byrne et al., 2016).
- 4 The fourth section aimed at measuring children's **psychological and social well-being** through two validated scales, namely the Stirling Children's Well-Being Scale (Liddle & Carter, 2015) and the Social Success Index (Pea et al., 2012).

Parent Questionnaire

The questionnaire designed for parents included 5 sections:

- 1 The first one was about the **access to digital technologies at home**, namely what digital devices are in the household and children's access to the devices.
- 2 The second section was about **parental mediation** strategies; it included items about enabling/active and restrictive mediation and parental monitoring retrieved from the Global Kids Online Modular Survey (Byrne et al., 2016).
- 3 The third section investigated the **coordination of schools and families** in educating children to use digital technologies in a safe and positive way.
- 4 The second last section asked parents about their **online activities** using the same items used in the child questionnaire.
- 5 The last section was about **digital skills** and knowledge and included an adaptation of the items in the Global Kids Online Modular Survey (Byrne et al., 2016).

Teacher Questionnaire

The questionnaire consisted of 6 parts:

- 1 The first section was about the **access to digital technologies at school**, namely the use of digital technologies during school time (*i.e. access to devices and school tasks*).
- 2 The second section was about **teacher's enabling/active mediation**, and it included items from the Global Kids Online Modular Survey (Byrne et al., 2016).
- 3 The third section investigated **school policies**, namely acceptable use policy and digital learning plan.
- 4 The fourth section investigated the **coordination of schools and families** in educating children to use digital technologies in a safe and positive way.
- 5 The second last section was about teacher's **online activities**.
- 6 The last section was about **digital skills and knowledge**.

Population and Sampling

The target survey populations were 10/11-year-old children, their parents and primary school teachers in the Republic of Ireland and Italy. The sampling was conducted via schools through convenience and *snowball sampling* strategies to facilitate the recruitment of all the three populations. The procedure consisted of involving 5th class pupils, their parents and all the teachers in the primary school with the support of a referral teacher. The recruitment started in September 2021, and it was slowed down by the disruption of school's activities due to the ongoing Covid pandemic and the work overload for teachers in the second half of the school year.

Surveys were carried out through three different methods for the three populations.

- Child Questionnaires were administered through both Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) and Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI) and Personal Assisted Personal Interview (PAPI) method. In 6 schools, children completed the survey online alone during school time (CAWI). In other 6 schools, children filled out the survey online on tablets/ laptop or desktop computers in the presence of the researcher (CAPI), whereas in two schools they completed the survey in paper format in the presence of a trained interviewer (PAPI) and in one school surveys were administered both through CAWI and PAPI methods.
- Parents' and teachers' questionnaires were administered through CAWI. Therefore, they completed the survey online on their digital devices alone while at home.

Details on data collection procedures are reported in the Appendix.

Participants

The study involved **722 children, 222 parents** and **128 primary** school teachers:

- 226 children were from the Republic of Ireland and 546 were from Italy. The mean age was 10.52 years ($SD= 0.60$). 49.3% were males, 48.4% were females and 2.3% reported other gender/ preferred not to say.
- 36 parents were from the Republic of Ireland and 186 from Italy. The mean age was 43.73 years ($SD= 5.73$). 14.9% were males, 82% were females and 3.2% preferred not to say.
- 36 teachers were from the Republic of Ireland and 92 from Italy. The mean age was 42.73 years ($SD= 11.44$). 5.5% were males, 93.7% were females and 0.8% preferred not to say.

Ethical Aspects

National rules and conditions were followed in each country during the data collection. The study obtained ethical approval from the University College Dublin Human Research Ethics Committee (UCD HREC). Information sheets were distributed to the recruited participants, and signed parental consent forms for minors were collected. Before starting the survey, participants had to give their informed consent to take part in the study. All participants were guaranteed anonymity and the possibility to withdraw at any time. Also, they were not forced to answer the questions. As for children, during the data collection efforts were made to provide a setting where they did not feel judged or evaluated and where they could feel comfortable and able to ask for any support if needed. Safeguards were put in place in the event of vulnerabilities arising.

Results

In this section, results are presented from the three different samples: children, parents, and teachers. Results will cover the components of the theoretical framework that has informed this research project, namely: online activities, children's safe and positive use of DT and well-being, media ecology in the households and schools (*i.e., availability of and access to DT*), adult mediation, family and school coordination regarding children's media education and teachers' perspective of school policies. Regarding the children's sample, gender differences were considered.

Children's Sample

Children's Online Activities and Positive Use of Technology

To investigate what children do online, the frequency of several activities was investigated, namely learning, creative, communication and entertainment. As shown in *Figure 1*, children's most frequent online activities were entertainment activities (i.e., watching videos and playing online games), whereas the least frequent activities were creative/production activities (i.e., creating their own video or music and uploading it to share and creating a blog or story or website online). Medium levels of frequency were reported for communication and learning online activities (e.g., searching information for doing homework). These trends were identified both in the Irish and in the Italian sample (see *Figures 2 and 3*).

Total Sample

FIGURE 1 Children's online activities (Total Sample).

Irish Sample

FIGURE 2 Irish Children's Online Activities.

Italian Sample

FIGURE 3 Italian Children's Online Activities.

When looking at gender differences, no significant differences were found between males and females, except for gaming which is slightly higher among boys. Non-binary children ($N=2$) reported that they engaged more frequently in creative and communication activities (*in particular, instant messaging*) (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4 Children's Online Activities (Frequency Means), Gender Comparison.

In terms of safe and positive use of digital technologies (SPUDT), children reported overall medium levels of positive use of digital technologies for all the 4 categories of online activities considered. Irish children tended to report slightly higher levels of positive use than Italian children (Figure 5).

Safe and Positive use of Digital Technologies

FIGURE 5 Levels of safe and positive use of digital technologies (means) for the four categories of online activities considered.

Levels of safe and positive use were relatively the same across genders except for safe and positive use during entertainment activities for non-binary children who reported lower levels (Figure 6).

Safe and Positive use of Digital Technologies

FIGURE 6 Irish Children's Online Activities.

Children's Well-Being

The association between levels of safe and positive use of digital technologies (*SPUDT*) and psycho-social well-being was tested through correlations.

	SPUDT during Learning Activities	SPUDT during Creative Activities	SPUDT during Communication Activities	SPUDT during Entertainment Activities	Psychological Well-being
SPUDT during Creative Activities	.44**	-			
SPUDT during Communication Activities	.69**	.46**	-		
SPUDT during Entertainment Activities	.65**	.44**	.71**	-	
Psychological Well-being	.35**	.23**	.40**	.42**	-
Social Well-being	.28**	.15**	.31**	.28**	.56**

TABLE 1 Correlation between safe and positive use of technologies for the four categories of online activities considered, psychological and social well-being.

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Significant moderated correlations were found between the measures of SPUDT for the four categories and psychological and social well-being, confirming a relationship between how technology is used and general well-being outcomes.

Regarding well-being, children reported medium levels of psychological well-being and high levels of perceived social success (i.e., social well-being). Irish children reported slightly higher levels of both dimension of well-being compared to Italian children (Figures 7 and 9).

FIGURE 7 Level of children's psychological well-being (means).

FIGURE 9 Level of children's social well-being (mean).

Children who defined themselves as non-binary reported lower level of psychological well-being (Figure 8) and social well-being (Figure 10).

FIGURE 8 Level of children's psychological well-being (means), gender comparison.

FIGURE 10 Level of children's social well-being (mean), gender comparison.

Digital Skills and Knowledge

Digital skills and knowledge are important competencies for children to fully benefit from the use of digital technologies and protect themselves from online risks and harms (ITU, 2018). In this section, children’s digital skills and digital knowledge levels will be presented by considering both the overall score and the single scores for each dimension, namely technical, programming, information, communication and production **skills**, and information, communication and production **knowledge**.

Children had on average a medium level of **digital skills**; Irish children reported slightly higher digital skills compared to Italian children. **Communication** and **interaction** digital skills were the most developed, whereas **programming** skills were the least developed both among Irish and Italian children (Figure 11).

Digital Skills

FIGURE 11 Levels of children's digital skills (means).

No significant differences were found regarding gender (see figure 12).

Digital Skills

FIGURE 12 Levels of children's digital skills (means), gender comparison.

Moreover, children reported on average a medium to low level of digital knowledge. Irish children tended to have a higher level of digital knowledge than Italian children (Figure 13).

Digital Knowledge

FIGURE 13 Levels of children's digital knowledge (means).

When gender differences are considered, non-binary children reported having lower information but higher communication knowledge (Figure 14).

Digital Knowledge

FIGURE 14 Levels of children's digital knowledge (means), gender comparison.

Adults Mediation

Children were asked about their perception of active and restrictive parental mediation and active teacher mediation.

Children perceived medium levels of both **active parental** and **teacher mediation**, and medium-low levels of **restrictive parental mediation** (Figures 15 and 17) with no differences across genders (Figures 16 and 18). Irish children tended to perceive higher levels of both parental and teacher active mediation strategies compared to Italian children, whereas Italian children perceived higher levels of restrictive parental mediation (Figures 15 and 17).

FIGURE 15 Mean frequencies of parental mediation strategies from children's perspective.

FIGURE 17 Mean frequency of teachers' active mediation strategy from children's perspective.

FIGURE 16 Mean frequencies of parental mediation strategies from children's perspective, gender comparison.

FIGURE 18 Mean frequency of teachers' active mediation strategy from children's perspective, gender comparison.

Parent's Sample

Children's access to Digital Devices at Home

As previously stated, ecological and socio-psychological models (Navarro & Tudge, 2022; Yardi & Bruckman, 2011) highlighted the importance of taking into account the characteristics of the environment when analysing children's online activities. What children do online cannot be separated from the availability of digital devices in their everyday lives' contexts and their access to those devices. For this reason, access and use of digital devices will be analysed considering both the family environment (presented below) and the school environment (presented in the next section).

Data collected from the sample of parents revealed that the most present **device in the households** is the smartphone. Indeed, there are on average 3.1 smartphones per household, followed by PCs/Laptops (1.9), tablets (1.4) and gaming consoles (1.28). However, if the two countries are considered separately, this pattern changes. Smartphone is the most present device both in Irish and Italian households (respectively 3.56 and 3.01 smartphones per household), the second most present device in Irish households is tablet (2.36 vs 1.21) whereas in Italian households is the PC/Laptop (1.88 vs 2.03). Overall, Irish households were more digitally-equipped than the Italian households (Figure 19).

FIGURE 19 Average number of digital devices in participants' household.

Regarding children's **access to digital devices**, 75.8% of parents declared that their 10/11-year-old child is allowed to use smartphone. However, the most accessed device is Tablet (96% of parents reported to let their child use it), followed by gaming console (86.9%) and PC/Laptop (86.5). This pattern is similar in the two countries, namely tablets are the most used devices by children in this age group.

When looking at the differences between Ireland and Italy, Irish children have access to gaming console more than PC/Laptop (respectively 90.9% and 88.6%) and Italian children have access to both PC/Laptop and gaming console to the same extent (respectively 86.1% and 86%). It is worth noting that when considering smartphones, 77.6% of Italian parents compared with 66.7% of Irish parents reported that they let their children use the smartphone (Figure 20). This is the only case in which Italian parents reported a higher percentage of usage compared with Irish parents.

Devices used by Children

FIGURE 20 Percentage of children who have access to different digital devices.

Another important aspect to consider is the **ownership** of digital devices. Gaming consoles resulted in being the most owned devices by children (66.8% of parents reported that their child personally owned a gaming console), followed by tablets (50.3%), smartphones (39.3%) and PC/Laptops (31.7%). Again, the two countries showed a different pattern: among Irish children, the most owned device was tablet (65.7% of parents reported that their child personally owned it) followed by gaming console (60.6%), smartphone (50%) and PC/Laptop (25.7%), whereas among Italian children the most owned device was the gaming console (68.2%) followed by the tablet (47%), the smartphone (37.2%) and the PC/Laptop (32.9%) (Figure 21).

Devices owned by Children

FIGURE 21 Percentage of children who own their own digital devices.

Parents' Online Activities

Figures 22, 23 and 24 show that parents use DT mostly for communicating with family and friends, working and learning. They use DT less for entertainment and almost never for creative purposes. Trends were similar across the two countries.

Total Sample

FIGURE 22 Percentages of parents engaging in different types of online activities.

Irish Sample

FIGURE 23 Percentages of Irish parents engaging in different types of online activities.

Italian Sample

FIGURE 24 Percentages of Italian parents engaging in different types of online activities.

Parents' Digital Skills and Knowledge

Parents reported a medium level of digital skills. The Irish sample reported slightly higher levels of digital skills than the Italian sample (Figure 25). The same applies for digital knowledge levels (Figure 26).

FIGURE 25 Level of parents' digital skills (mean).

FIGURE 26 Level of parents' digital knowledge (mean).

Parental Mediation

Parents were asked about their active, restrictive and monitoring strategies to regulate children's access to DT. Parents reported medium levels of **active**, **restrictive** and **monitoring** strategies which highlights that they put in place a combination of all three strategies to regulate their children's use of DT. Italian parents reported slightly higher levels of active and restrictive mediation strategies, whereas Irish parents reported higher levels of monitoring strategies (Figure 27).

Parental Mediation

FIGURE 27 Mean frequencies of parental mediation strategies.

Family-School Coordination (Parents' Perspective)

Parents reported medium-high levels of **family-school coordination** (i.e., perception of alignment between family and school) in educating children on how to use DT in a safe and positive way (Figures 28, 29 and 30).

Total Sample

FIGURE 28 Parents' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

Irish Sample

FIGURE 29 Irish parents' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

Italian Sample

FIGURE 30 Italian parents' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

Teacher's Sample

Children's access to Digital Devices during School time

Teachers reported that the most used device in school was PC/Laptop (65.4% of teachers reported children can use it at school) followed by tablet (47.2%). A very small percentage of teachers reported that children can use smartphones and gaming consoles at school (respectively 2.4% and 0.8%). Interestingly, these figures are substantially different between the two countries.

As shown in Figure 31 below, PC/Laptop and tablets are equally accessed by Irish children at school with nearly all the teachers reporting their pupils have access to these devices (94.4% both) and none of the Irish teachers reported children using either smartphones or gaming console.

In Italy, half of the Italian teachers stated that children can access PCs/Laptops in class (53.8%). Tablets followed with 28.6%, and a very small percentage of teachers reported that children use smartphones (3.3%) and gaming consoles (1.1%). In other words, children in Irish schools have a much higher access to digital devices like tablets or laptops compared with Italian children, yet in both cases there is no access to smartphones and gaming consoles (Figure 31).

Devices used by Children during School time

FIGURE 31 Percentage of teachers reporting their pupils have access to digital devices in school.

School Activities Online

Regarding school activities that teachers ask pupils to do online, the three most frequent activities were as follows: **A** - practising with something they were learning, followed by **B** - communicating with teachers (*e.g.*, *submitting homework or asking a question*), and **C** - writing. The three least frequent activities were: **A** - chatting online, **B** - contributing to a school blog or to online discussion and **C** - making presentations.

However, differences emerged between Italy and Ireland: The three most frequent activities Irish pupils are asked to do by their teacher were: practising what they were learning, communicating with teachers and doing group work with other students, whereas Italian pupils were most frequently asked to practise what they were learning, writing and checking out information on the school website. Overall, Irish teachers reported asking pupils to do school activities online more frequently than the Italian teachers, except for checking out information on the school website and chatting online (*Figure 32*).

FIGURE 32 Average frequency of school activities teachers ask pupils to do using digital technologies.

Teachers' Online Activities

Teachers' most frequent activities online were learning and working activities, followed by communication activities. They used DT less for entertainment and almost never for creating content online. Trends were the same in the two countries (Figures 33, 34 and 35).

Total Sample

FIGURE 33 Percentages of teacher engaging in different types of online activities.

Irish Sample

FIGURE 34 Percentages of Irish teachers engaging in different types of online activities.

Italian Sample

FIGURE 35 Percentages of Italian teachers engaging in different types of online activities.

Teachers' Digital Skills and Knowledge

Teachers reported a medium level of **digital skills** and **knowledge**. The Irish sample reported slightly higher levels of digital skills and higher digital knowledge than the Italian sample (*Figures 36 and 37*).

FIGURE 36 Level of teachers' digital skills (mean).

FIGURE 37 Level of teachers' digital knowledge (mean).

Teacher Mediation

Teachers reported medium levels of active mediation with Irish teachers showing slightly higher levels than Italian teachers (*Figure 38*).

Teacher's Mediation

FIGURE 38 Mean frequency of teachers' active mediation.

Family-School Coordination (Teachers' Perspective)

Teachers reported medium-low levels of alignment with parents in teaching children how to use digital technologies in a safe and positive way. Irish teachers reported higher levels of family-school coordination than Italian teachers (Figures 39, 40 and 41).

Total Sample

FIGURE 39 Teachers' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

Irish Sample

FIGURE 40 Irish teachers' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

Italian Sample

FIGURE 41 Italian teachers' perception of coordination between family and school in educating children about the use of digital technologies (percentage of agreement).

School Policies and Curriculum

Three aspects related to school policies and curriculum were investigated. Teachers were asked about their satisfaction with the acceptable use policy (AUP) and the digital learning plan (DLP) in place in their schools. Moreover, they were asked if Internet safety was taught in their school.

Teachers reported medium levels of satisfaction with both AUP and DLP. If the two countries are considered separately, Irish teachers reported relatively higher level of satisfaction with both AUP and DLP, whereas Italian teachers reported medium levels. Differences are bigger regarding the DLP (Figure 42).

FIGURE 42 Teachers' satisfaction with DT use policy and digital learning plan in school (means).

Overall, the 87.5% of teachers reported that **Internet safety** was taught at school. If the two countries are considered separately, all Irish teachers reported that Internet safety is part of their school curriculum; while, it is worth noting that almost 20% of Italian teachers reported that Internet safety **is not part** of their school curriculum (Figure 43).

FIGURE 43 Percentage of teachers saying that Internet safety is taught in school.

Discussion

General Considerations

Data presented in this report was collected in a particularly challenging moment for schools and families since it happened at the end of the last wave of COVID-19. This created challenges in recruiting schools and, in particular, actively involving parents and teachers in completing the survey since they felt overwhelmed by the global crisis caused by the pandemic. Despite acknowledging these limitations, we were able to reach a very good number of families in the two participating countries, Ireland and Italy.

The findings illustrated in this report can provide a snapshot of an important post-pandemic trend on children's, parents' and teachers' skills, knowledge, and use of technologies, which can be worth continuing to explore in the coming months and years.

Access to Digital Technologies

Smartphones are the most present digital devices in households in both Ireland and Italy. Irish households are more digitally equipped than Italian households. However, **pre-adolescents are more likely to have access to tablets than smartphones**, with the former being the most frequently used device both in Ireland and Italy. DT are also used for school activities, with Irish teachers availing of technologies for different learning and communication activities more than Italian teachers.

As highlighted by previous research, our results showed that when asking about the preferred tool to go online smartphone is the preferred device among 9 to 16-year-olds, yet the use of smartphones increases significantly at 12-14 years of age and even more at 15-16 years (e.g., *Smahel et al., 2020*). This happens since parents of pre-adolescent are reluctant to give pre-adolescents access to personal smartphones, instead they allow children to access tablets, computers, and game consoles.

Online Activities, Children's Positive Use of DT and Well-being

The three samples of children, parents, and teachers both in Italy and Ireland showed similar patterns of online activities, with parents and teachers doing more learning/work and communication activities, and children doing more **entertainment activities online**. Overall, Irish sample reported a higher frequency of online activities, except for creative activities which were slightly more frequent among Italian teachers. As for school activities, Irish teachers asked children to use DT for school purposes (e.g., *making presentations, creating content, doing group work with other students, etc.*) more frequently than Italian teachers.

It can be argued that the COVID-19 pandemic brought changes in digital practices, especially for school-related activities: having been forced to move classes online could have pushed teachers and children to find new ways of embedding digital technologies in teaching and learning practices. It is arguable that those practices have been carried over time as if they were *'normal'* routines even after the emergency of Covid-19 pandemic ended.

We also included analysis on **children's well-being (psychological and social)** finding an association between children's well-being and safer and positive use of DT.

No differences were found between male and female pre-adolescent regarding the types of online activities they engaged with. Pre-adolescents who defined themselves as non-binary showed significantly higher engagement in creative and communication online activities (see *De Coninck & d'Haenens's, 2023*). Lastly, as for the **positive use of DT**, Irish children reported slightly higher scores than Italian children across the four categories of activities, namely learning, creative, communication and entertainment activities. **Non-binary** pre-adolescents differentiated from the others for showing less positive DT use during entertainment activities.

These children showed also lower levels of well-being; this could be due to gender identity exploration. However, our sample was too limited to generalise this result. As also indicated below, further research should investigate further these dimensions in non-binary youth.

Digital Skills and Knowledge

Digital skills and knowledge levels emerged as **higher in the Irish sample** of children, parents and teachers than in the Italian samples. These results are consistent with children's access to digital technologies and frequency of online activities: the literature shows that more access to DT and more frequent online activities are associated with higher digital skills (Haddon et al., 2020). In this sense, the **Irish samples reported more access to DT** for children and more frequent online activities in general. No significant differences were found except for information (*lower*) and communication (*higher*) digital knowledge in **non-binary pre-adolescents**.

A possible explanation is that these children use social media for exploring further their gender identity and socialising given the prevalence of binary and heteronormative models in the '*physical world*.' More research is needed to examine this important aspect in child development and technology use.

Adult Mediation Strategies

Mediation strategies were investigated from the perspectives of children, parents, and teachers, yet teachers were asked about active strategies only. Data was not directly comparable across the three target groups because children answered a shorter version of the mediation scales. However, we can assume that the perceptions about the **combination of active and restrictive mediation** strategies are similar across the samples: in general, it emerged that active mediation is more frequent than restrictive mediation.

The combination of different mediation strategies is documented in the literature (Livingstone & Helsper, 2008; Pfetsch, 2018) and it reflects both the need to help children understand how to use DT and, at the same time, restrict those aspects of technologies that are considered inappropriate for their age.

Family-School Coordination

The comparison between parents and teachers' perception regarding **family-school coordination** in educating children about the use of DT showed that parents report a slightly higher level of alignment with teachers. In other words, parents believe that the regulation of their children's use of DT does not differ from what teachers do in school. This confirms that parents believe they have a **good coordination with teachers** for DT practices; while, in line with what was found in the literature (Beilmann et al., 2020), teachers seem to be less optimistic about the collaboration with families.

This may suggest the need to increase occasions for teachers and parents to share educational practices regarding the use of DT. **Recent initiatives have been launched in both countries:** in Italy, "*Patti Digitali*" is a community-based educational initiative that brings schools and parents together to set shared rules on when and how to give their children access to digital devices and online platforms (<https://pattidigitali.it/>).

Something similar has been developed in Greystones, Ireland, where parents' associations across the district's primary schools have shared and adopted a no-smartphone code. Similar initiatives have spread across different Irish primary schools and caught the attention of the Department of Education.

The Department has recently published guidelines to facilitate parents' engagement with schools and communities to discuss rules about digital technologies, in particular smartphone access and use for primary school children (Department of Education, 2023).

School Policies

Schools play a central role when it comes to digital transformation and education. In Ireland, the **"Digital Strategy for School to 2027"** and in Italy the **"Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale"** are country-level plans that aim at providing schools with a strategy to embed DT in teaching and learning and to develop children's skills and competencies to be active and responsible users. It seems that in Ireland the development of Acceptable Use Policies and Digital Learning Plan has been successful, since our results showed that teachers are generally satisfied with school digital policies.

In Italy, the process of embedding digital technologies in teaching and learning has been recently updated (<https://scuoladigitale.istruzione.it/pnsd/>); however, according to Italian teachers there is still work that needs to be done.

Conclusions

This report presented a snapshot of **children's digital skills** and associated dimensions with the aim to better understand how to promote children's safer and positive use of DT (*Digital Technologies*). Despite the focus of this work being on **children's practices with DT**, we also wanted to investigate **parents' and teachers' practices**, their knowledge, and their skills with DT. Adults have a central role in regulating the access and use of technologies, and adults' practices shape the ways in which children interact with digital devices and the Internet (Everri, 2017; 2018; Livingstone & Blum-Ross, 2020).

Our findings provided evidence on parents' and teachers' extensive use of DT for different purposes (e.g., *communication and work activities*). Also, it was reassuring to find that both in Ireland and Italy, parents engage in open communication with their children about the use of DT and privilege active mediation strategies or a combination of restrictive and active mediation. In other words, they engage in conversations with their children about what they do online, explain the risks and benefits of DTs, but they also apply rules for screen time, use Internet filtering software, and limit the access to specific content, such as games not suited for their age.

As for **restricting the access to smartphones**, which is a key topic in the current public debate especially for children attending primary schools³, we found that both in Ireland and Italy the number of children with access to smartphones in primary schools is limited compared with the access to other devices. In line with other reports (e.g. Beresford et al., 2023), pre-adolescents are given access to **tablets or computers**. This is in line with parents' and teachers' tendency to restrict the access of children of this age to smartphone for their children's/pupils' safety and protection.

Adults' concerns for children's safety and protection are legitimate: The need to regulate the access to digital devices is undeniable. However, from a psychosocial perspective and as outlined by other research studies (e.g., Haddon et al., 2020) a **'banning approach'** to smartphone might prevent children from developing

better digital skills. Our results showed that the only way for children to develop better digital skills is to use digital devices and engage in online activities. In other words, the more children have the possibility to interact with digital devices and the Internet, the more they can become **'digitally competent'**, namely develop technical and communication/interpersonal skills (e.g., *how to open an account online, how post comments, how to block unwanted content or report/talk to someone about a negative experience happened online*). Also, from an education perspective, a punitive approach based on rigid rules, such as banning or confiscate phones, can trigger the circumvention of the rules and foster children's engagement in *'clandestine'* activities, such as using older children's phone, stealing parents' phones, and, ultimately, exacerbate parent-child conflict (Everri, 2018; Everri, 2017). All this can be detrimental to children's safety and protection.

Therefore, centring the current debate on banning the access to smartphones for safety and protection concerns might not allow children to learn, develop better skills, and eventually use technologies for good (entertainment, study, creative activities, socialising). While acknowledging the imperative need for regulations, we suggest that a better way to look at this phenomenon is to focus on the **type of experience** that children have online, while providing them with information about the **different types of DT since an early age**. In the context of primary schools, children can be guided to explore smartphones or any other device gradually. For instance, they can be instructed on understanding what smartphones are, how they work, what they can find once they approach the device, and what can happen when using different functions. We should be mindful that children see us using smartphones constantly, and their curiosity for those devices start from a very early age.

In this sense, **parents and teachers should be both engaged** in providing role models for fostering a positive use of digital devices among children. As reported above, our findings are reassuring since in both countries there is a good level of collaboration between families and schools regarding DT education,

3 For Ireland: 'Keeping Childhood Smartphone Free', Department of Education, 2023.

and adults' regulation strategies (*mediation*) are based on a combination of open communication and restriction. However, **more should be done to foster children's digital skills** since these skills can develop only when children practice with using technologies, including smartphones.

Families and schools should continue to work together to find the best **strategies to foster children's/pupils' skills development** while regulating DT use through information, communication, and monitoring. However, this should be done considering **children's perspectives and rights** to benefit from the opportunities offered by technologies. We encourage families and schools to develop initiatives around technologies in **which also children are involved** (*not only parents' meetings, as often happens*): children are the primary stakeholders, and they have a lot to say about DT and their experiences when opportunities to make their voices heard are offered.

However, schools' and families' education function cannot happen in isolation: the **broader community, governmental institutions and media providers** have a role to play. More specifically, youth associations, sport clubs, NGOs and charities concerned with children's education, health and wellbeing should include DT education in their programmes as an added value to their core activities. For example, sport clubs could become places for conversations about online games, for example FIFA or similar, by organizing formal events that also involve parents. Furthermore, coaches could be encouraged to talk to children about the positive and negative aspects of using DT during training (e.g. respecting privacy in the changing room by not taking photographs or recording videos). Sport clubs can therefore be another important context, together with family and school, to promote an informed and safe use of DT.

The **media industry** has the duty to design technologies that allow children to be safer and protected. A **'safety by design'** approach, which puts **children's safety and right to be secure and protected online**, is now imperative.⁴ There has been

ongoing debate among tech companies on the need to become more attuned to children's safety and protection; however, the actual implementation of such measures seems too slow to tackle ongoing risks and harm for children. In this sense, Governments have the duty to provide protection of their citizen's rights by actively legislate on the issue. Legislation on DT and children has made progresses over the last few years (e.g. *the EU Audiovisual media Directive*); however, more needs to be done. First, for children to develop better digital skills, the use of technologies should be promoted together with media education as an integral component of the school curriculum since pre-school/ kindergarden.

Secondly, appropriate legislation needs to be applied to media providers to guarantee that their services comply with EU regulations on children's rights and protection measures. The European **Digital Service Act** and the **Digital Markets Acts**⁵ have been recently approved and will come into effect shortly: this legislation will oblige tech companies, such as Meta and TikTok, to provide more information on the measures they have taken for risk assessments and mitigation to protect minors online, in particular with regard to the risks to mental health and physical health, and on the use of their services by minors.

In conclusion, the old African saying, **'it takes a village to raise a child'** continue to be an appropriate metaphor also for contemporary digitised societies: Considering that now **children live their lives online** and offline it is our duty to provide them with the best opportunities to thrive both online and offline. This is possible only when all social actors ('the villagers') are involved in their different roles and functions (i.e., media providers, schools, families, youth associations, etc.,) in sustaining children's development which also (now) include becoming **competent and responsible digital citizens**.

⁴ For more details on safety by design on the recent UK Bill on 'Secure by design' see Livingstone, S., & Pothong, K. <https://digitalfuturecommission.org.uk/blog/uk-secure-by-designvs-australian-safety-by-design/>

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-services-act-package>

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Appendix

Theoretical Framework (Activity Theory)

Data Collection Procedure

School	Country	Method for Data Collection (<i>Children</i>)		
		CAWI	CAPI	PAPI
School 1	Italy		X	
School 2	Italy		X	
School 3	Italy	X		X
School 4	Italy		X	
School 5	Italy			X
School 6	Italy		X	
School 7	Italy			X
School 8	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 9	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 10	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 11	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 12	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 13	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 14	Rep. of Ireland		X	
School 15	Rep. of Ireland		X	

School	Country	Method for Data Collection (<i>Parents</i>)		
		CAWI	CAPI	PAPI
School 1	Italy	X		
School 2	Italy	X		
School 3*	Italy			
School 4	Italy	X		
School 5	Italy	X		
School 6	Italy	X		
School 7	Italy	X		
School 8	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 9	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 10	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 11	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 12*	Rep. of Ireland			
School 13	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 14	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 15*	Rep. of Ireland			

* No data collected from parents.

School	Country	Method for Data Collection (<i>Teachers</i>)		
		CAWI	CAPI	PAPI
School 1	Italy	X		
School 2	Italy	X		
School 3	Italy	X		
School 4	Italy	X		
School 5	Italy	X		
School 6	Italy	X		
School 7	Italy	X		
School 8	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 9	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 10*	Rep. of Ireland			
School 11	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 12*	Rep. of Ireland			
School 13	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 14	Rep. of Ireland	X		
School 15	Rep. of Ireland	X		

* No data collected from teachers.

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